

Studies on Haloaromatics and Haloheterocyclics. Synthesis of Halogenated 1, 3, 4-Oxadiazole-2-Thiones and Fluorinated Acridines as Possible Fungicides

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Three 5-aryloxymethyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazole-2-thiones, fifteen 3-haloarylamino-methyl-5-aryloxy-methyl-1, 3, 4-oxadiazole-2-thiones and fifteen 5-fluoroarylamino acridines have been prepared. Out of these twenty seven compounds have been screened for their antifungal activity against '*Aspergillus niger*' and '*Aspergillus flavus*'. All of them have been found to possess antifungal activity.

5-SUBSTITUTED-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-ones(I) and 3-substituted aminomethyl-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-ones(II) have been found to exhibit antimycobacterial^{1,2} as well as fungicidal activity³. Due to a structural analogy between compounds of the type (I) and their sulphur analogues (III) and compounds of the type (II) and their sulphur analogues (IV) it was speculated that 5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones (III) and 3-substituted aminomethyl-5-substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones (IV) might be biologically active. Further since there is a close pharmacological relationship between physiology of fungi and mycobacteria, compounds of the type (III) and (IV) might also be active against fungi.

Such compounds have $>N-C(=S)O-$ group and $>C-O-C<$ moiety which are perhaps responsible for their fungicidal activity.

Keeping this in view we have synthesised 5-aryloxy-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones and 3-haloarylaminomethyl-5-aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones as potential fungicides.

5-Aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones (III) were prepared according to the method of Young and

Wood⁴ and were subjected to Mannich reaction by condensing them in absolute ethanolic solution with formaldehyde and various halogenated primary amines to give 3-haloarylamino-methyl-5-aryloxy-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones (IV). The site of the substituent in these compounds (IV) has been arrived at by analogy⁵.

Usually, an unsubstituted nucleus containing heterocyclic nitrogen is seldom fungitoxic. Acridine is, however, known to be toxic to spores of various rusts⁶. Horsfall and Rich⁷ found acridine to be fairly active against *Sclerotinia fructicola* and *Macrosporium sarcinaeforme*. Acridine derivatives have been found to act as fungicides⁷, insecticides⁸⁻¹¹, bactericides¹², medicinals¹³ and as carcinogenic¹⁴ compounds. Keeping this in view we have prepared 5-fluoroarylaminoacridines¹⁵ by the condensation of substituted-5-chloroacridines¹⁶ with fluoroanilines in phenol.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected.

Aryloxy acetyl hydrazines

These were prepared by the method of L. Conti¹⁷.

5-Aryloxymethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones

An aryloxy acetyl hydrazine (0.05M) was added to an aqueous solution of KOH [(0.05M) dissolved in 10 ml. of H₂O]. To this 20 ml of ethanol were added. A clear solution was obtained. To this carbonyl-sulfide (1M) was added and the resulting mixture refluxed for six hours. It was concentrated to a small volume and then filtered. This filtrate on acidification with cold 4N HCl gave a solid which was filtered, washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol.

The compounds thus prepared are listed, along with their relevant data, in Table I.

TABLE 1. 5-ARYLOXYMETHYL-1, 3, 4-OXADIAZOLE-2-THIONES

S.No.	Name	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	%N		%S	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1. ^a	5-(<i>p</i> -Chlorophenoxyethyl)1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	140	75.8	C ₉ H ₇ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	11.38	11.54	13.34	13.19
2.	5-(<i>o</i> -Tolyloxyethyl)1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	97	78.5	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.46	12.61	14.35	14.41
3.	5-(<i>p</i> -Tolyloxyethyl)1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	150	80.0	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	12.52	12.61	14.38	14.41

IR Spectral data ν_{max} in cm⁻¹

α .	S=C-N 3300	C=N 1600	C=S 1070	Paradisubstituted benzene ring 860	C-Cl 755
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3-Haloarylaminoethyl-5-aryloxyethyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiones

5-Substituted-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione (0.01M) was dissolved in a minimum of absolute ethanol and kept in an ice-bath. To this 1 ml. of formaldehyde (40%) was added. An aromatic amine (0.01M), dissolved in minimum of absolute ethanol, was then added slowly to this ice-cold mixture. The resulting mixture was swirled gently and then left in the ice-bath for 3 hr. The precipitated solid was filtered off and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol.

The compounds thus prepared are listed, along with their relevant data, in Table 2.

5-Fluoroarylamino-acridines

A mixture of a substituted-5-chloroacridine (0.01M), phenol (0.1M) and fluoroarylamine (0.01M) was heated for 6 hr at 100°. It was cooled, triturated with ether and filtered. The residue [the hydrochloride of 5-fluoroarylaminoacridine] was washed several times with ether and dried. To get the free base it was dissolved in acetic acid. The resulting solution was decomposed with ammonia and the solid separating out, filtered, washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol.

The compounds thus prepared are listed, along with their relevant data, in Table 3.

TABLE 2. 3-HALOARYLAMINOETHYL-5-ARYLOXYETHYL-1, 3, 4-OXADIAZOLE-2-THIONES

S.No.	Name	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	%S		%N	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	3-(<i>o</i> -Chlorophenylaminoethyl)-5-(<i>p</i> -chlorophenoxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	115	91.8	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	8.40	8.38	11.02	10.99
2.	3-(<i>m</i> -Chlorophenylaminoethyl)-5-(5-chlorophenoxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	126	65.4	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	8.25	8.38	11.20	10.99
3.	3-(<i>p</i> -Chlorophenylaminoethyl)-5-(<i>p</i> -chlorophenoxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione	108	85.4	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ Cl ₂ N ₃ O ₂ S	8.30	8.38	9.98	10.99
4.	3-(<i>m</i> -Fluorophenylaminoethyl)-5-(<i>p</i> -chlorophenoxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	95	85.3	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ ClFN ₃ O ₂ S	8.54	8.75	11.11	11.22
5.	3-(<i>p</i> -Bromophenylaminoethyl)-5-(<i>p</i> -chlorophenoxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	110	80.8	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ BrClN ₃ O ₂ S	7.39	7.50	9.90	9.85
6.	3-(<i>o</i> -Chlorophenylaminoethyl)-5-(<i>o</i> -tolylloxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	68	65.4	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	8.90	8.85	11.54	11.62
7.	3-(<i>m</i> -Chlorophenylaminoethyl)-5-(<i>o</i> -tolylloxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	82	65.8	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	8.75	8.85	11.35	11.62
8.	3-(<i>p</i> -Chlorophenylaminoethyl)-5-(<i>o</i> -tolylloxyethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	105	60.8	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	8.64	8.85	11.80	11.62

TABLE 2. (Contd.) 3-HALOARYLAMINOMETHYL-J-ARYLOXYMETHYL-1, 3, 4-OXADIAZOLE-2-THIONES

S.No.	Name	m.p. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	%S		%N	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
9.	3-(<i>m</i> -Fluorophenylaminomethyl)-5-(<i>o</i> -tolylloxymethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	109	90.8	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ FN ₃ O ₂ S	9.03	9.27	12.20	12.17
10.	3-(<i>p</i> -Bromophenylaminomethyl)-5-(<i>o</i> -tolylloxymethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	79	85.4	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	7.76	7.88	9.98	10.34
11.	3-(<i>o</i> -Chlorophenylaminomethyl)-5-(<i>p</i> -tolylloxymethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	105	88.9	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	8.80	8.85	12.10	11.62
12.	3-(<i>m</i> -Chlorophenylaminomethyl)-5-(<i>p</i> -tolylloxymethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	98	78.4	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	8.93	8.85	11.59	11.62
13. ^a	3-(<i>p</i> -Chlorophenylaminomethyl)-5-(<i>p</i> -tolylloxymethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	108	91.3	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ ClN ₃ O ₂ S	8.93	8.85	11.10	11.62
14.	3-(<i>m</i> -Fluorophenylaminomethyl)-5-(<i>p</i> -tolylloxymethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	118	90.0	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ FN ₃ O ₂ S	8.30	9.27	12.30	12.17
15.	3-(<i>p</i> -Bromophenylaminomethyl)-5-(<i>p</i> -tolylloxymethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thione.	128	92.3	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ BrN ₃ O ₂ S	7.80	7.88	10.38	10.34

 IR Spectral data, γ_{max} in cm⁻¹

	S=C-N	C=N	C=S	Paradisubstituted benzene ring	C-Cl
a.	3300	1600	1280	820	720

TABLE 3. 5-FLUOROARYLAMINOACRIDINES.

S. No.	Name	HCl salt		Yield %	Molecular formula	%N	
		m.p. °C	m.p. °C			Found	Calcd.
1.	5-(4'-Fluorophenylamino)acridine	220	92	57.3	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ FN ₂	9.64	9.72
2 ^a .	5-(3'-Fluorophenylamino)acridine	210	85	50.8	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ FN ₂	9.59	9.72
3.	5-(4'-Fluorophenylamino)-3-methylacridine	250	76	49.3	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ FN ₂	9.32	9.27
4 ^b .	5-(3'-Fluorophenylamino)-3-methylacridine	240	172	50.1	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ FN ₂	9.10	9.27
5.	5-(4'-Fluorophenylamino)-3-methoxyacridine	250	98	49.2	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ FN ₂ O	8.67	8.74
6.	5-(3'-Fluorophenylamino)-3-methoxyacridine	250	70	42.1	C ₂₀ H ₁₅ FN ₂ O	8.62	8.74
7.	5-(4'-Fluorophenylamino)-3-chloroacridine	250	75	38.8	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClFN ₂	8.48	8.68
8.	5-(3'-Fluorophenylamino)-3-chloroacridine	250	180	45.7	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClFN ₂	8.56	8.68
9.	5-(4'-Fluorophenylamino)-3-bromoacridine	250	185	37.9	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ BrFN ₂	6.79	6.73
10.	5-(3'-Fluorophenylamino)-3-bromoacridine	250	195	35.8	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ BrFN ₂	6.60	6.73
11.	5-(3'-Fluorophenylamino)-3-nitroacridine	250	191	29.5	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ FN ₃ O ₂	8.22	8.40
12.	5-(4'-Fluorophenylamino)-3,8-dichloroacridine	250	240	40.5	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ FN ₂	8.85	8.96
13.	5-(3'-Fluorophenylamino)-3,8-dichloroacridine	250	218	50.8	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ Cl ₂ FN ₂	9.10	8.96
14.	5-(4'-Fluorophenylamino)-3-bromo-8-chloroacridine.	250	120	38.9	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ BrClFN ₂	6.85	6.97
15.	5-(3'-Fluorophenylamino)-3-bromo-8-chloroacridine.	250	95	38.8	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ BrClFN ₂	6.78	6.97

 IR Spectral data γ_{max} in cm⁻¹

	Secondary-NH	C=N	Metadisubstituted benzene ring
a.	3300	1600	850
b.	3400	1500	820

 NMR Spectral data
1.9—3.5 τ

a. Aromatic protons

Biological Activity

Fungicidal test

Twenty seven compounds have been screened for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* and *Aspergillus flavus* by agarplate technique¹⁸ at three different concentrations namely 1:1,000, 1:10,000 and 1:100,000. Although all the compounds displayed antifungal activity, only compounds 1 and 3 of Table 1 showed significant results.

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References

1. A. E. WILDESMITH and E. FROMMEL, *Arzneimittel Forsch.*, 1962, 12, 22, 275 and 485; *U.S. Pat.*, 2,758,117/1956; *Chem. Abs.*, 1957, 51, 3670.
2. H. C. CALDWELL, R. J. SEIWALD and J. H. BURKHALTER, *J. Amer. Pharm. Assoc., Sci. Edn.*, 1958, 47, 799.
3. A. SUGIHARA and S. TSUBONCHI, *Japan*, 1967, 7542.
4. R. W. YOUNG and K. H. WOOD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 400.
5. T. R. VAKULA and V. R. SRINIVASAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 583-87.
6. STRAIB, *Zentral. Bakt. Abst.*, 1941, 2, 103.
7. J. G. HORSEFALL and S. RICH, *Boyce Thomson Institute*, 1951, 16, 316.
8. V. PREY, F. BERAN and H. BOHM, *Mitt. Chem. Forsch. Inst. Wirtschaft Osterr.*, 1952, 6, 28.
9. W. D. STEWART and J. H. STANDEN, *U.S.* 2, 510, 431, June 6, 1950, *Chem. Abs.*, 1950, 44, 8591b.
10. K. C. JOSHI and M. K. THOLIA, *Agr. Biol. Chem.*, 1974, 38, 1165.
11. K. C. JOSHI and S. O. BAHREL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 38, 877.
12. N. G. PH. BUU-HOI and P. JACQUIGNON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 4173.
13. J. H. WILKINSON and I. L. FINAR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1947, 759; 1948, 288.
14. R. M. BRADLOW and C. A. VANDERWERF, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 654.
15. K. SINGH and G. SINGH, *Indian J. Pharm.*, 1952, 13, 47.
16. "Organic Synthesis", Vol. VIII, p. 53.
17. L. CONTI, *Chem. Abs.*, 1964, 61, 4253e.
18. U.S.D.A., *Circular No.* 198, 1931.